

Fast-Track Report REDMANE Data Ingestion Project

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1. Introduction

This fast-track report is designed to help new interns quickly understand the REDMANE Data Ingestion project and start contributing within 6 hours. It goes over what is needed to get up to speed with the current state of the project, from why we are doing it to the latest implementation.

1.1 What is REDMANE?

REsearch Data Management and ANalysis Environment (REDMANE) is like a

Library Analogy: Just as a library catalogue tracks books across multiple physical locations without storing the books themselves, REDMANE tracks research data files across different organisations while the actual files remain in their original locations.

The system stores only metadata (information about files such as size and location) while the data itself is stored locally with each organisation. As new data is generated, from raw to processed to summarised versions, the metadata is updated in the registry so that researchers from different organisations that are collaborating can see the status and location of files. There are links from the registry to visualisation portals for easy viewing of summarised data once projects have been completed e.g. cBioPortal for genomics data and OMERO for imaging data. There are also links from the local directories to the data registry as well as links back from the portals to the registry so that the data is connected across all platforms and can be found regardless of where you start.

2. The Problem We're Solving *Time to read: 20 minutes | Ask supervisor questions after reading*

2.1 Why REDMANE Exists

Modern biomedical research generates enormous amounts of data across multiple institutions. Key challenges and how REDMANE addresses them:

1. **Data is scattered across different organisations (WEHI, MCRI, etc.)**
 - Only tracking the metadata so that data can be found while still being stored across different organisations
 - Avoids problem of trying to centrally store very large datasets and making the system lightweight to adopt, with minimal changes to existing research infrastructure set up.
2. **Multiple data types (WGS, scRNA-seq, imaging) with different formats**
 - Researchers can specify which file types they are interested in tracking by including those file extensions when first registering the dataset.
 - This makes REDMANE very flexible and adaptable to diverse projects as well as emerging technologies that may have different formats by not having strict file type expectations.
3. **Researchers struggle to find datasets across labs**
 - When in the local directory, researchers will be able to see a link to the data registry which shows them other datasets that are part of the project, even if they are stored at a different organisation.
 - From the data registry, researchers can see information about all datasets that they have permission to access.

- Data portals are open to the general research community. From there, anyone can see a link back to the registry, so outside researchers that are interested in the results also have a way to contact the organisation hosting the raw data.

4. Data managers need easy tools to register and track files

- The workflow for ingesting and uploading the metadata needs to be easy to use for widespread adoption.
- REDMANE includes a metadata generator script for finding and recording files of interest within a directory, organising the information into Json format for addition to a SQL database.

2.2 Where the Data Ingestion Team fits in

- Our team scopes requirements for and improves on the metadata generator script
- Coordinates with the web dev team to ensure the output format matches what is expected for upload to the data registry
- Coordinates with the workflows team to ensure the synthetic datasets generated for demo purposes work with the metadata generator

2.3 Requirements for the Metadata Generator

Functional:

- Scan dataset directories containing research files, return files with matching extensions
- Categorise files as raw, processed, or summarised
- Extract metadata (file names, sizes, patient/sample IDs)
- Performs patient to sample mapping for each file
- Generate JSON metadata for the Data Registry
- Create human-readable HTML report

Quality Attributes:

- **Ease of use:** visual preview, minimal user action required
- **Flexibility:** easy to work with new file types and on new systems
- **Maintainability:** modular code, unit tests, clear branching strategy
- **Reliability:** handles unexpected input gracefully, logs errors
- **Performance:** can process thousands of files in under 5 mins

3. System Architecture *Time to read: 30 minutes | Ask supervisor questions after reading*

3.1 Architecture Diagram

Additional organisations connect to the data registry in the same way.

3.2 Components

Data Registry (ReactJS + FastAPI + PostgreSQL) in Docker container

- The central catalogue that stores metadata about patients, samples, datasets, and files.

Metadata Generator (Python)

- Our main tool - scans directories, extracts metadata, generates JSON and HTML outputs.
Key files:
- update_local_v1.py - Main entry point and functions
- generate_html.py - HTML report generation

Portals

Visualization tools that connect to the Data Registry:

- cBioPortal - Genomics data visualization (mutations, expression, copy number)
- OMERO - Imaging data visualization and management

3.3 Current Implementation *Time to explore: 30 minutes*

Visit this link for a walkthrough of the current implementation and what each part of the map looks like in detail: [REDMANE diagram overview.pptx](#) (will also be uploaded to Zenodo if you can't access the sharepoint)

3.4 Changes made during Summer 2025 2026 intake

1. Config file introduced:

Previous	Problem	Changes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variables hard coded in a file in the script repo Patient sample mapping a separate file that needs to be loaded 	Variables need to be edited each time you run on a new directory and new dataset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A config.json file specific to each project directory placed in that folder Also loads patient sample mapping A directory key helps verify it is in the correct folder

- Will be in future created automatically by the data registry for download as a source of truth
- Opens up API usage in future

2. Update_local_v1.py refactored:

Previous	Problem	Changes
OS library used for file paths	Would break on another operating system	Pathlib library used for paths instead to be OS agnostic
Individual functions for processing raw, processed, summarised files	Not modular or efficient: 3 directory walks and a lot of repeated code	Modular code: 1 walk of the directory, 1 function for extracting metadata and doing mapping
Assumes sample ID is the same as filename without the file extension	Fails if not exact match	Regex to search for sample ID within filename and inside file
Some redundant features	Increased storage	ROCrates and organisation as a field removed (no WEHI compatibility for ROCrates so no longer a use case)

3. HTML design updated:

- Old:** https://github.com/Jess-Sun/REDMANE-metadata-generator-with-RO-Crate/blob/jess-refactor/test_WGS/output.html
- New:** https://github.com/Jess-Sun/REDMANE-metadata-generator-with-RO-Crate/blob/amanda-demo-ingestion/test_WGS/output.html

4. Validation of inputs added:

- Checks target directory matches directory in config file
- Check file extensions are present in config file

1. Testing added:

- Introduced unit tests and integration tests, continuous integration workflow with pytest and GitHub Actions

3.5 Potential Future Work *Time to read and think: 30 minutes | Think about if these changes make sense in context and suggest alternatives if disagree, ask supervisor questions to clarify objectives*

For future data ingestion teams:

- Python package of the metadata generator for easier installation
- R version and package of the metadata generator since R commonly used in research
- Handling of other research file types that require reading into the file to extract sampleIDs
- Changes to how files with multiple associated sampleIDs such as counts, are displayed in the html preview

For future web development teams:

- Patient to sample mapping could be done inside the data registry instead
- Functionality to create and download the config file from the data registry does not exist yet
- Potentially an API to communicate the contents of the config file to the metadata generator (however authentication is needed to ensure security and may be troublesome over CLI)

4. Quick Start Guide *Time to complete: 60 minutes | Stop and ask for help if stuck for more than 15 minutes***4.1 Setup (15-30 minutes)****Step 0: Set up Github account and SSH access if not done already**

Can follow this guide: [Version Control with Git - MBITE Tutorials](#)

Step 1: Clone the Repository

```
# Clone the team repository
git clone https://github.com/Jess-Sun/REDMANE-metadata-generator-with-RO-Crate.git
cd REDMANE-metadata-generator-with-RO-Crate
# Checkout the summer branch
git checkout 14-2025-2026-summer
```

Step 2: Set up and activate virtual environment

- **Run the Tool (15-30 minutes)**

Run tool following instructions in repo README and view outputs:

<https://github.com/Jess-Sun/REDMANE-metadata-generator-with-RO-Crate/blob/amanda-demo-ingestion/README.md>

5. Your Next Steps

- Complete the Quick Start (60 min)
- Read Key Resources and other teams quick starts for the larger picture understanding of REDMANE
- Read the code (30 min): Review `update_local_v1.py` to understand the flow
- Agree on a GitHub branching strategy with Rowland and the team before making any changes

Questions to Ask Your Supervisor

- Any questions that help you understand WHY you are doing something
 - What are the goals for the current intake vs what are nice to have for the future
- Remember to CC all team mates when sending an email to Rowland regarding the project

6. Key Resources**6.1 Essential Reading**

Resource	Time	Description
Intake Landing Page	20 min	Project overview and quick start
REDMANE Introduction Deck	45 min	75-slide comprehensive overview
Intake 14 Zenodo Page	90 mins	Fast track reports from other REDMANE teams
WEHI RCP FAQ	15 min	Answers to common questions